

**Predicted Effects and Cost-effectiveness of Wheat Flour Fortification for Reducing
Micronutrient Deficiencies, Maternal Anemia, and Neural Tube Defects in Yaoundé and
Douala, Cameroon**

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Keywords: Micronutrient, Fortification, Folic Acid, Neural Tube Defect, Anemia, Cameroon,
Cost-effectiveness

1 **ABSTRACT**

2 **Background:** Policymakers aiming to reduce micronutrient deficiencies (MNDs) and their
3 health effects must choose among alternative definitions of impact when evaluating cost-
4 effectiveness.

5 **Objective:** Estimate the cost-effectiveness of a mandatory wheat flour fortification program for
6 reducing cases of MNDs (iron, zinc, folate, vitamin B12), anemia and neural tube defects
7 (NTDs) averted, and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) averted in urban Cameroon.

8 **Methods:** A 13-year predictive model was developed, including a 3-year startup period and 10
9 years of program activity. Costs were estimated using historical program budgets. Effects were
10 calculated based on observed changes in prevalence of MND and anemia one year post-
11 fortification, and predicted reductions in neural tube defects (NTD) based on NTD burden and
12 wheat flour intake. Total DALYs averted were estimated for anemia and NTDs.

13 **Results:** The program cost ~\$2.4 million over thirteen years and averted an estimated ~95,000
14 cases of maternal anemia and ~83,500 cases of iron deficiency among children after one year.
15 Cost/case-year averted for MNDs ranged from \$0.50 for low plasma folate to \$3.30 for iron
16 deficiency and was \$2.20 for maternal anemia. The program was predicted to avert 1,600 cases
17 of NTDs over 10 years at ~\$1,500/case averted. Estimated cost/DALY averted was \$50 for
18 NTDs and \$115 for anemia.

19 **Conclusions:** In Cameroon, cost-effectiveness of wheat flour fortification varied by the measure
20 of impact employed, but was classified as “very cost-effective” for all outcomes using WHO
21 criteria. Policymakers and their advisors must determine how best to use information on program
22 costs and benefits to inform their decisions.

23

24 INTRODUCTION

25 While micronutrient deficiencies (MND) affect millions of people around the world,
26 women and children in low- and middle-income countries disproportionately bear this burden¹.
27 Iron deficiency is estimated to be the leading contributor of anemia worldwide², zinc and vitamin
28 A deficiencies increase the risk and severity of morbidity among young children¹, and vitamin B12
29 deficiency impairs neurological development. Additionally, maternal folate insufficiency around
30 the time of conception increases the risk of infants being born with neural tube defects (NTDs).
31 Strategies such as food fortification, supplementation, and promotion of naturally nutrient-rich
32 foods have been implemented worldwide to address this problem.³ To select an appropriate MND
33 control strategy for a given country, decision-makers with limited resources must not only examine
34 the potential effectiveness of each intervention, but weigh its cost-effectiveness in comparison to
35 alternative micronutrient interventions, as well as in comparison to other priority nutrition and
36 health interventions.

37 Fortification is consistently reported to be a highly cost-effective intervention, with
38 estimates as low as pennies per person reached per year by fortified products^{4,5,6}. However, reliance
39 on this indicator alone may fail to capture the potential health impact of a program. That is, it is
40 possible that an individual reached by fortified foods did not have inadequate intake prior to
41 fortification; conversely, someone with inadequate intake may not consume sufficient quantities
42 of the fortified food to achieve adequate micronutrient intake. Thus, when the desired outcome is
43 to reduce MND and associated health consequences, cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) should
44 endeavor to use metrics that more accurately reflect the health benefits of the program. Ideally, the
45 estimated benefits would come from rigorous, population-based effectiveness studies. Where this
46 information is unavailable (often the case, particularly for new intervention programs), analyses

47 can be based on predicted rather than observed effects on health outcomes, with predictions often
48 made in the absence of detailed data on the coverage of fortified foods and fortification levels
49 achieved. On the other side of CEA calculations, program costs are often estimated in the absence
50 of actual program budgets. Thus, studying post-hoc cost-effectiveness using actual impacts and
51 costs is useful to confirm the cost-effectiveness of an intervention.

52 Cameroon is one of few countries with nationally-representative information on dietary
53 intake and pre-fortification prevalence of MND,⁷ data on prevalence of MND and anemia post-
54 fortification,⁸ and documentation of program costs.⁹ Specifically, multiple MNDs were observed
55 among women and young children in a national survey in 2009, including anemia prevalence
56 among women of reproductive age (WRA) of 46.7%.⁷ While data on the prevalence of NTDs are
57 limited in geographic scope, available data suggest that the prevalence of NTDs in Cameroon from
58 1997-2006 was four times that of the US at 1.99/1000 cases per year,^{10,11} . A marked improvement
59 in the micronutrient status among WRA and children in urban Cameroon was observed after
60 mandatory wheat flour fortification was implemented in 2011.⁸ Although we are not aware of post-
61 fortification data on NTD prevalence, a significant decrease in the number of these cases has been
62 predicted.¹¹

63 The objective of our analysis was to calculate the cost-effectiveness of mandatory wheat
64 flour fortification with iron, folic acid, zinc, and vitamin B12 for reducing MNDs, anemia, and
65 NTDs in urban Cameroon. We used data on wheat flour intake and observed changes in MND and
66 anemia prevalence, as well as predicted reductions in NTD prevalence to develop a 13-year
67 predictive model to evaluate the cost per case of MND, anemia, or NTD averted. We also estimated
68 disability-adjusted life years (DALY) of anemia and NTDs averted by wheat flour fortification,
69 and cost per DALY averted, and compared each of these measures of the cost-effectiveness to the

70 cost per individual reached by the program. Note that we refer to ‘cases’ of MND throughout the
71 paper for simplicity, but we recognize that biomarkers such as plasma folate reflect recent intake
72 or ‘exposure’ and not necessarily ‘deficiency’ and that these measures (particularly plasma folate,
73 vitamin B12, and zinc) are not intended for individual diagnosis but instead should be used for
74 population assessment. Acknowledging these limitations, we used this approach to quantify the
75 population-level effects of the fortification program.

76

77 **METHODS**

78 We estimated the costs and nutritional benefits of a mandatory wheat flour fortification
79 program in the two major urban areas in Cameroon (Yaoundé and Douala) over a period of 13
80 years, from 2009 to 2021. Wheat flour was mandated to include iron (60 mg/kg, as ferrous
81 fumarate), zinc (95 mg/kg as zinc oxide), vitamin B12 (0.04 mg/kg), and folic acid (5 mg/kg) based
82 on WHO standards¹². Introduction of fortified wheat flour in Cameroon occurred in 2011 after a
83 3-year process of planning and implementation.⁹ The chosen 13-year time frame includes 3 years
84 of implementation preparation, during which startup costs were incurred but fortified products
85 were not yet available in the market, and 10 years of projected benefits and continued program
86 costs thereafter.

87 The benefits of wheat flour fortification included in our analysis are expressed as person-
88 years of reach of wheat flour fortification; case-years of MND and anemia averted; NTDs averted;
89 and DALYs averted due to reductions in NTD and anemia for two target groups: women of
90 reproductive age and preschool children. Estimates of wheat flour reach were derived from a 2009
91 national dietary intake survey, and applied to the target populations in Yaoundé and Douala to
92 estimate the number of women and preschool children reached.⁷ For MND and anemia, the pre-

93 and post-fortification prevalences of each outcome were measured in Yaoundé and Douala in 2009
94 and 2012⁸, and the difference in prevalence, where statistically significantly different from zero,
95 was applied to the target population. Population data were obtained from the Lives Saved Tool
96 (LiST).¹³ The predicted proportion of NTD cases averted by flour fortification with folic acid was
97 estimated using data on dietary intake of wheat flour and pre-fortification NTD birth prevalence.¹¹
98 The specific methods used to estimate intervention program costs and benefits are described
99 below.

100 **Costs**

101 Cost data for the wheat flour fortification program in Cameroon were gathered from Helen
102 Keller International-Cameroon budget documents, as described previously.⁹ Start-up and recurring
103 costs were estimated as annual country-wide totals for wheat flour fortification over the 13-year
104 period (2009-2021). Costs began in 2009 with the baseline survey to assess the need for
105 fortification (by measuring micronutrient status and dietary intake) and additional start-up costs
106 accrued from 2009 to 2011 before flour fortification was fully implemented in 2011, after which
107 recurring costs were incurred for program implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Costs were
108 divided into 12 categories: Startup costs include the baseline survey, industrial assessment,
109 revision of standards, equipment for industry, equipment for the national lab, press conference
110 before the launch, launching ceremony, and training of partners and stakeholders; recurring costs
111 include micronutrient premix, monitoring and evaluation, supervision costs, and other indirect
112 costs.

113 To match costs to the geographic area for which we had benefit estimates, we applied a
114 spatial weight of 31.7% to country-wide costs to define program costs for Yaoundé and Douala.
115 This spatial weight was based on the total consumption of wheat flour products in Yaoundé and

116 Douala relative to other regions observed in the fortification baseline survey.^{7,9} We chose to
117 allocate costs based on consumption rather than population or square kilometers per geographical
118 area because the vitamin/mineral premix accounts for the largest portion (almost 80%) of the total
119 cost of the flour fortification program and is purchased in proportion to the amount of wheat flour
120 to be fortified, and the populations in Yaoundé and Douala consume a disproportionate amounts
121 of wheat flour relative to their population sizes. Thus, we judged this weighting approach to be the
122 most appropriate way to ‘scale’ national program costs to Yaoundé and Douala.

123 **Reach of wheat flour**

124 Results of the 2009 national survey of dietary intake in Cameroon were used for estimates
125 of the reach of wheat flour in Yaoundé and Douala. Reach was defined as the proportion of WRA
126 or preschool children with reported consumption of wheat flour-containing products (bread, fried
127 dough, etc.) in the previous 7 days. These proportions were then applied to the urban population
128 estimates generated by the Lives Saved Tool (as described below) to calculate the number of
129 person-years reached by wheat flour over time.

130 **MNDs and anemia**

131 We calculated the cases of MND and anemia averted annually using results from previous
132 studies which collected data on MND prevalence in Yaoundé and in Douala 2 years prior
133 (baseline/pre-fortification in 2009) and 1 year after (post-fortification in 2012) introduction of the
134 wheat flour fortification program⁸ (Table 1).

135 For our modeling, the baseline prevalence of each outcome in 2009 was applied to each
136 year before 2011, when fortified products were introduced. The magnitude of decrease in the post-
137 fortification prevalence (observed in 2012) was assumed to have been sustained thereafter. The
138 outcomes included in this analysis include low plasma folate (defined as <10 nmol/L), iron

139 deficiency (inflammation-adjusted plasma ferritin concentration <12 µg/L for children or <15 µg/L
140 for women), low plasma zinc (children: <65 µg/dL for morning samples and < 57 µg/dL for
141 afternoon samples; women: <50 µg/dL for pregnant women, < 70 µg/dL for morning fasted
142 samples, <66 µg/dL for morning nonfasted samples, and <59 µg/dL for afternoon samples),
143 vitamin B12 deficiency (<148 pmol/L), and anemia (hemoglobin concentration <110 g/L for
144 children and pregnant women; <120 g/L for nonpregnant women) ⁸. Outcomes that were not
145 significantly different between pre- and post-fortification surveys (i.e., P>0.05) were not included
146 in our analysis. For example, no statistically significant difference was observed for anemia
147 prevalence among children, so we did not model benefits of anemia reduction among children.
148 Differences in prevalence of each outcome before and after flour fortification in Yaoundé and
149 Douala were translated to number of case-years averted – and further to cost per case-year averted
150 – by utilizing population data from the Lives Saved Tool (LiST) extracted for the MINIMOD
151 project.^{9,13} Population estimates for WRA and children (age 6-59 months) for 2011-2021 were
152 extrapolated back to 2009 for this analysis. We note that applying the cost for the full program
153 (i.e., multiple micronutrient fortification) as the numerator for each MND overestimates the cost
154 (and thus underestimates cost-effectiveness) for that individual nutrient since the same platform
155 actually delivers several nutrients (i.e., iron, zinc, folic acid and vitamin B12) and the amounts of
156 all nutrients added are reflected in the premix cost. The estimates generated for cost per MND
157 averted can be interpreted as the cost effectiveness of the program for addressing deficiency of a
158 single micronutrient.

159 **NTD prevalence**

160 To our knowledge, there has not been a study to assess post-fortification NTD prevalence
161 in Cameroon. Thus, we used predictions for post-fortification NTD reduction using the “Expanded

162 LiST Model”, as described by Luo *et al*¹¹ This predictive model accounts for the following factors:
163 1) annual live births and stillbirths, 2) pre-fortification NTD birth prevalence, 3) effective coverage
164 of wheat flour fortification (proportion of WRA who achieve adequate folate intake due to wheat
165 flour fortification), estimated using national dietary intake data,⁷ and 4) effectiveness of
166 fortification or supplementation for reducing NTD birth prevalence (i.e., 62%, derived from meta-
167 analyses and applied to the proportion of the population effectively covered).^{11,14}

168 We obtained estimates of annual live births in Yaoundé and Douala, Cameroon, from
169 LiST¹³. Pre-fortification (1997-2006) NTD-affected live birth prevalence was determined to be
170 1.99 per 1000 live births in a retrospective study in selected urban areas in Cameroon.¹⁰ Pre-
171 fortification NTD stillbirth prevalence in Cameroon was unavailable and was thus estimated by
172 applying the proportion of NTD stillbirths to NTD live births reported for Sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁵
173 Using this information, the predictive model estimated for Yaoundé and Douala 1) the number of
174 NTD cases (calculated as prevalence of NTD live and still births times the number of NTD live
175 births) and 2) the percentage of NTD cases averted (calculated as effective coverage times
176 effectiveness) for the 10-year post-fortification period¹¹. Finally, we combined these estimates
177 with total program costs for Yaoundé and Douala to calculate dollars per case of NTD averted.

178 The nutritional impact of fortification relies on whether the food vehicle is fortified at the
179 target fortification levels. However, the interim evaluation study in 2012 found that the folic acid
180 content in wheat flour was at 75% of the target fortification level (5 mg/kg),⁸ and more recent data
181 suggested that the folic acid fortification level was less than 50% of the target level.¹⁶ Thus, to
182 produce a more conservative estimate, we assumed for calculation of predicted NTD cases averted
183 that wheat flour was fortified at 50% of the target level. Wheat flour fortification levels of 25%,
184 75%, and 100% of the target folic acid levels were also applied as a separate sensitivity analysis

185 to estimate DALYs averted due to NTD reductions. For each scenario, we modeled effective
186 coverage of wheat flour fortification with different levels of folic acid (e.g., 25% of target, 50% of
187 target, etc.) and used the resulting effective coverage values to model NTDs averted, as described
188 in Luo *et al*¹¹.

189 **DALYs: NTDs**

190 Annual years of life lost (YLLs) and years lived with disability (YLDs) averted from
191 NTDs in Yaoundé and Douala were calculated using the method described by Fox-Rushby and
192 Hanson (with parameters $K=1$, $r=0.03$, and $\beta=0.04$).¹⁷ Stillbirths were assumed to represent
193 death at age zero, where $YLD = 0$ and $YLL = DALY$. NTD-affected live births averted were
194 broken down by NTD subtype to account for different disability weights for each subtype.
195 Proportions of spina bifida, anencephaly, and encephalocele among NTDs averted were
196 estimated from regional prevalence data in Sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁵ Disability weights for spina
197 bifida and anencephaly were obtained from the Global Burden of Disease study.¹⁸ Disability
198 weight for encephalocele was unavailable but assumed to be equal to that for spina bifida. Given
199 that years of disability are relatively low in these conditions due to the high case fatality rate, this
200 assumption is unlikely to greatly influence the final estimate of DALYs.

201 To determine duration of disability and life expectancy for live births, regional
202 prevalence rates in Sub-Saharan Africa were used to estimate the percentage of live birth NTDs
203 that resulted in death under the age of five versus death over the age of five for each subtype.¹⁵
204 These proportions were applied to the number of NTD live births averted in our study. We
205 conducted a sensitivity analysis to calculate low, medium, and high estimates for deaths under
206 age five and deaths over age five. The low estimate assumed death under age five to occur at five
207 years and death over age five to occur at 58 years (the average life expectancy in Cameroon for

208 the general population).¹⁹ The midpoint estimate assumed death under age five to occur at 2.5
209 years, and death over age five to occur at 26.5 years. Finally, the high estimate assumed death
210 under age five to occur just after birth and death over age five to occur at five years. YLLs and
211 YLDs from each subtype of NTD were ultimately combined to achieve an NTD total. Low,
212 medium, and high estimates of DALYs were calculated for each year and respectively summed
213 to generate total DALYs over the 10-year post-fortification duration.

214 **DALYS: Anemia**

215 DALYs for anemia were calculated as described above for NTDs, with the major
216 difference being that we expressed anemia DALYs per case-year rather than per case (i.e.,
217 duration of disability as 1 year), as the diagnosis is considered to represent a short-term
218 condition, rather than a permanent condition. Given that anemia may occur or resolve at any age
219 among WRA, the age weighting factor was set to zero. Anemia was not considered a direct cause
220 of death in this analysis, therefore $YLL = 0$ and $YLD = DALY$.

221 Proportions of mild, moderate, and severe anemia were obtained from data collected in
222 2009 in Yaoundé and Douala.⁷ Mild cases comprised 53.8% of cases, moderate cases comprised
223 42.9%, and 3.3% of cases were severe. Reanalysis of data from the 2012 survey suggested a shift
224 toward a greater proportion of cases of mild anemia;⁸ however, for simplicity, cases of anemia
225 averted were assumed to follow the same distribution of severity as observed in 2009. Disability
226 weights for each class of severity of anemia were obtained from the Global Burden of Disease
227 estimates.¹⁸ Total YLDs were calculated annually ($K=0$, $r=0.03$, $\beta=0$) and combined over the
228 13-year time frame to generate total DALYs from anemia averted.

229 **Discounting**

230 Total costs, total population reached, total cases of MNDs, anemia, or NTDs averted, and
231 total DALYs averted were each discounted at 0%, 3%, and 6% as a sensitivity analysis. Discounted
232 cost per case and cost per DALY averted were generated by matching costs and benefits with the
233 same discount rate (i.e. 6% cost/DALY is generated from 6% discounted costs and 6% discounted
234 DALYs). DALYs for NTDs and anemia were also discounted at a 3% rate within each year.¹⁷

235

236 **RESULTS**

237 The combined population of Yaoundé and Douala, Cameroon in 2012 was 4,909,950,
238 including 1,252,245 WRA and 538,901 children 6-59 months of age. The total estimated cost of
239 the fortification program for Yaoundé and Douala over 13 years was \$2,439,000 (Table 2). The
240 cost of the flour premix alone comprised the largest portion of the total costs (77.9%), which is
241 comparable to the percentage of total costs of flour fortification estimated for other programs. In
242 all, 82.3% of the total costs were for ongoing costs such as annual micronutrient premix costs and
243 routine monitoring and evaluation that happen every 3-5 years. The remaining 17.7% of total costs
244 were start-up costs for monitoring/evaluation, supervision, and indirect costs of office rent and
245 other materials.

246 Approximately 98% of WRA reported consuming wheat flour in the previous 7 days;
247 based on this estimate, 1.75 million WRA and preschool children would be reached by wheat
248 flour during the first year of the program (Table 3). In the first year of implementation, the wheat
249 flour fortification program was also estimated to have averted more than 95,000 cases of anemia
250 among WRA, based on the observed reduction in anemia prevalence from 46.7 to 39.1%, and
251 83,000 cases of iron deficiency among children (Table 4). In addition, there were large predicted
252 reductions in the number of WRA and children with low plasma folate (440,000), vitamin B12

253 deficiency (100,000), and low plasma zinc (320,000). Assuming a sustained impact of the
254 fortification program, we predicted that over one million case-years of anemia among WRA
255 would be averted over the subsequent 10 years of program implementation.

256 Over 10 years, the program was predicted to cost \$0.12 total per woman or child reached
257 (Table 5). The cost per case-year of MND averted is also presented in Table 5; total program cost
258 are applied to each nutrient, attributing the cost to implement a program to that nutrient alone. Low
259 plasma folate averted was predicted to be the most cost-effective outcome for WRA and children
260 combined (\$0.49/case-year) and iron deficiency averted was the least cost-effective (\$3.27/case-
261 year). In addition, the program was predicted to avert 1,600 NTD cases over 10 years, costing
262 \$1,530 each (Table 6). This corresponds to 49,310 DALYs of NTD averted with a range of 48,500
263 to 50,040 DALYs based on optimistic and conservative estimations of life expectancy and duration
264 of disability, as described in the methods (Table 7). Each DALY averted due to NTDs was
265 estimated to cost \$49.50 (\$48.70-\$50.30, depending on the assumptions used in calculating
266 DALYs). An additional 21,310 DALYs are predicted to have been averted from anemia among
267 WRA, costing \$114.50 per DALY (Table 7). In total, an estimated 70,620 (69,810-71,350) DALYs
268 were averted from anemia and NTDs combined, at an average cost of \$34.50 (\$34.20-\$34.90) per
269 DALY.

270 If all wheat flour were fortified at 100% of target levels throughout the modeled time
271 period, instead of 50% of the target levels, an estimated 55,050 DALYs from NTD would be
272 averted at a cost of \$44.30/DALY assuming that program costs remained the same (Table 8). In
273 contrast, wheat flour fortified at only 25% of target levels would avert 36,700 DALYs
274 (\$66.50/DALY).

275

276 **DISCUSSION**

277 We predicted the effects and cost-effectiveness of wheat flour fortification in Cameroon
278 for reducing MND and disabilities due to anemia and NTDs over a 13-year period, including 3
279 years of program startup and 10 years of program implementation. While the program was
280 estimated to cost \$0.12 per woman or child reached, the cost-effectiveness for achieving other
281 outcomes differed substantially: the cost per MND averted ranged from \$0.48 to \$3.27 per case-
282 year averted, depending on the nutrient and target group (WRA or child). In addition, reduction in
283 anemia cases among women was estimated to cost \$2.22 per case averted, the cost per case of
284 NTD averted was estimated at \$1,530 per case averted, and the cost for reducing DALYs from
285 anemia and NTDs was \$114.50/DALY averted and \$49.50/DALY averted, respectively. Despite
286 methodological differences among studies, as described below, our analysis is consistent with
287 other literature suggesting that industrial food fortification is cost-effective relative to other
288 nutrition and health interventions.^{4,5,6,20} In addition, the estimates of cost per MND case-year and
289 DALY averted are substantially less than the GNI per capita of Cameroon (\$3,640 in 2017),
290 meeting criteria for a “very cost-effective” intervention as defined by the WHO.²¹ Moreover, they
291 are below the standard threshold of \$150/DALY averted (~\$220 current value) suggested by the
292 World Bank²². Since nearly one-fifth of program costs were at start-up, we anticipate the cost-
293 benefit will become increasingly favorable with each year, if the estimated program impacts are
294 sustained.

295 Our estimate of cost per person reached is consistent with prior estimates of \$0.01 for folic
296 acid fortification, \$0.20 for vitamin A supplementation, and \$0.10-\$0.12 for iron fortification.⁶
297 However, this study and prior work also showed that the cost-effectiveness estimates for a given
298 intervention program are different when alternative outcome measures are examined; in some

299 cases, the ranking of cost-effectiveness among programs changed as the “definition of success”
300 changed⁹. This finding is expected, as only a subset of those reached would be expected to
301 experience deficiency that is resolved by food fortification, and indicates that policymakers and
302 their advisors must consider the ultimate goals of the program in deciding which outcome is most
303 appropriate for their situation and hence which “definition of success” is most appropriate for a
304 cost-effectiveness analysis.

305 Because few CEA of food fortification present estimates of cost per case of MND averted,
306 it is difficult to compare our results with others. However, other studies have presented cost-
307 effectiveness analyses using outcomes meant to capture the health impact of micronutrient
308 interventions.^{23,24} One analysis estimated that the hypothetical cost per case of scurvy averted can
309 range widely from \$158-\$1200, depending on the target population.²³ This high cost is not
310 surprising considering the rare occurrence of scurvy, and low number of vitamin C-deficient
311 beneficiaries that would be served by vitamin C fortification. In addition, antenatal micronutrient
312 supplementation in low- and middle-income countries was estimated to cost \$39-\$85 per case of
313 adverse pregnancy outcome averted.²⁴ Though imperfect comparisons, our results suggest that
314 large-scale fortification is a cost-effective means for reducing MND and associated health effects.

315 DALYs are widely accepted as a measure of disease burden that can be used to compare
316 and prioritize across health interventions. Our estimate of \$114.50/DALY averted for anemia is
317 slightly greater than that reported in other studies of large-scale food fortification. For example, a
318 study in China reported that iron fortification cost \$66/DALY averted and iron supplementation
319 cost \$179/DALY for an observed reduction of iron deficiency.²⁵ A study in Tanzania showed that
320 iron supplementation was highly cost-effective in preventing severe anemia at \$21/DALY
321 averted.²⁶ Other literature suggests that micronutrient interventions generally cost \$50-\$100 per

322 DALY averted²⁰, and thus are considered “very cost-effective” according to the WHO definition.
323 ²¹ The higher cost per DALY averted in this analysis could be because our predictions rely on
324 observed changes after implementation of wheat flour fortification, whereas studies that apply
325 effect sizes from controlled efficacy trials may result in optimistic predictions of the impact of a
326 large-scale program. In practice, cost-effectiveness may also differ between urban and rural areas,
327 or by other subnational designations that are associated with the reach, effective coverage, or levels
328 of compliance of fortified foods. We note that the somewhat low compliance rates observed for
329 folic acid concentrations also apply to the other nutrients included in wheat flour (~75% of target⁸),
330 so greater compliance might have been expected to yield greater impacts on micronutrient status
331 and possibly anemia prevalence. As a result, because the cost estimates were based on the cost of
332 the target amounts of premix, our results may slightly underestimate the cost-effectiveness of
333 fortification at target levels. Importantly, the model assumes that the same effects on micronutrient
334 status are sustained over time, so ensuring program compliance is critical to realize the predicted
335 benefits.

336 Given the low birth prevalence of NTD in comparison with conditions such as anemia, the
337 cost to avert one case is relatively high at \$1,530. However, the heavy burden associated with each
338 case of NTD results in a low cost per DALY averted (\$49.50/DALY). Our result is comparable to
339 that of an ex-poste study in Chile that reported \$89/DALY of NTD averted in a similar fortification
340 program.²⁷ Estimates for a hypothetical folic acid fortification program in Zambia, based on data
341 from South Africa, indicated a cost of \$14.90/DALY averted; however, sensitivity analyses
342 included an estimate of \$46.86/DALY, which is similar to our results.⁵ The lower hypothetical
343 cost/DALY averted of Zambia can be explained by several variables. First, their methods apply
344 data from South Africa - where significant reduction in NTD prevalence has been documented -

345 to Zambia, where folic acid fortification is not mandated, which could overestimate the impact of
346 the program if fortification compliance is below targets (as we assumed in this analysis for
347 Cameroon). Second, the analysis for Zambia assumed that all NTD cases result in immediate death,
348 which would result in a greater number of DALYs per case averted, compared to our method,
349 which considered cases of survival below and beyond 5 years.

350 Strengths of our analysis in comparison to other CEA calculations include the availability
351 of data on observed changes in MND and anemia prevalence after food fortification, detailed
352 dietary intake data to predict the change in NTD prevalence, and program budgets to inform cost
353 predictions. However, there are also several limitations, including those related to the data inputs.
354 As with any modeling exercise, there are numerous sources of uncertainty; thus, the point estimates
355 calculated here should be interpreted with caution. Although statistical confidence intervals were
356 available for some modeling inputs (such as micronutrient deficiency prevalence or reach); for
357 others, notably program costs, only single estimates are available so we could not calculate true
358 confidence intervals for the cost-effectiveness estimates. Where possible, however, we included
359 sensitivity analyses to assess the extent to which certain assumptions were likely to affect the
360 conclusions.

361 We limited the geographic scope of our analysis to two major urban areas of Yaoundé and
362 Douala, consistent with availability of information on micronutrient deficiency before and after
363 fortification. However, industrial food fortification is typically implemented at the national level,
364 so we needed to apply assumptions to estimate the cost of regional program from national cost
365 data. While this is not a realistic situation since fortification programs are rarely regional in scope,
366 since the cost of micronutrient pre-mix made up nearly 80% of total program costs, we considered

367 that dividing total national costs based on regional wheat flour consumption was appropriate to
368 generate cost-effectiveness estimates for the urban region studied.

369 Additionally, the estimates of change in micronutrient status come from pre-post cross-
370 sectional surveys, so one cannot be certain that the observed changes were attributable to the
371 fortification program. In particular, we assumed that the change in anemia prevalence among
372 women was attributable to the nutrients provided by wheat flour (primarily iron, but theoretically
373 also vitamin B12 and folic acid), recognizing that anemia has numerous causes, including malaria
374 in this setting. However, plausibility analyses of the data suggest that it was reasonable to conclude
375 that the observed changes were attributable.⁸ For example, frequency of wheat flour consumption
376 was associated with plasma vitamin B12 concentrations among both WRA and children after
377 fortification was in place, but this association was not observed one year earlier, prior to initiation
378 of wheat flour fortification with vitamin B12. We are not aware of other large-scale interventions
379 or policies that were implemented around the same time frame and would have influenced
380 micronutrient status or anemia prevalence; nevertheless, there remains the possibility that other
381 interventions or secular changes in dietary patterns may have contributed to the observed
382 differences.

383 An additional limitation is that data on erythrocyte folate concentration were not available,
384 which would enhance the estimation of NTD risk. Instead, we relied on predictions of the number
385 of NTD cases averted using an expanded version of the LiST model analysis, as described by Luo
386 and colleagues.¹¹ This method has the advantage of using detailed dietary intake analyses to
387 determine the proportion of the population affected, but a limitation is that it applies a fixed percent
388 reduction in NTDs based on meta-analysis of existing studies and does not take into account
389 estimation of “folic acid-preventable” NTDs.^{11,28} The conclusions of a review of NTD predictive

390 models suggested that this is a reasonable choice for settings in which data on erythrocyte folate
391 concentrations are not available.¹¹ Thus, we applied our best estimate using the limited data
392 available, but further studies must be done to validate these findings.

393 In calculating DALYs for anemia, we assumed that the change in anemia prevalence
394 among women was attributable to the micronutrients provided by the fortification program (as
395 noted above), and, further, the distribution of severity of anemia cases averted is proportional to
396 the distribution of severity of anemia cases in the population. With this approach, estimation of
397 DALYs does not take into account improvement in severity of anemia. For example, no DALYS
398 would be averted if a moderate case becomes a mild case; this may have led to an underestimation
399 of benefits. On the other hand, if only cases of mild anemia are averted by an iron intervention
400 (e.g., if severe anemia is mainly caused by infections such as malaria rather than iron deficiency)
401 then this approach would overestimate the disability burden since the disability weight for mild
402 anemia is much smaller than that for severe anemia (although severe anemia represented only 3%
403 of cases).

404 Finally, the results of this study assume that the fortification program continues to be
405 implemented as observed in 2012. However, more recent data suggests that the concentrations of
406 micronutrients in wheat flour dropped from 75% to less than 50%¹⁶, which has implications for
407 the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of the program – even at a lower percentage of
408 fortification, the result is a less cost-effective fortification program. To produce a conservative
409 estimate, the NTD predictions used for our analysis assumed that flour was fortified at 50% of
410 target fortification levels. However, if the coverage rate continues to decline, then the fortification
411 program will become less cost-effective. This observation emphasizes the importance of quality
412 of implementation of a fortification program, consistent with a recent review that concluded that

413 continued interest and investment by governments are required to ensure sustained impact of
414 efficient and cost-effective food fortification programs and that there is room for improvement in
415 coverage and quality of delivery, as well as measuring progress of national programs²⁹.

416 **Conclusion**

417 This modeling analysis indicates that, according to thresholds suggested by WHO, wheat
418 flour fortification in Cameroon is a very cost-effective means of reducing the disease burden of
419 MNDs, anemia, and NTDs in the country. Based on observed changes one year into the program,
420 the cost-effectiveness ranged from \$0.12 per individual reached and from \$0.49 to \$3.27 per case-
421 year of MND averted, depending on the micronutrient assessed. The program was also estimated
422 to cost \$48.70-\$50.30 per DALY averted due to NTDs, and \$114.50 per DALY averted due to
423 anemia. Sustained monitoring and support to the program are needed to ensure that these benefits
424 are maintained. Policymakers and their advisors should consider the costs, benefits, and co-
425 benefits associated with micronutrient intervention programs in making their decisions.

426

427 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENT**

428 AN, BW, HL, JK, SV, RES designed the analysis; JK, AN, JGA, MN, RES contributed to data
429 acquisition; AN, BW, HL, JK analyzed data; AN and BW drafted the paper; all authors
430 contributed to data interpretation and critically reviewed the manuscript. The authors thank
431 Kenneth Brown (UC Davis) and Ann Tarini (Independent Consultant) for helpful comments on
432 preliminary results, Katherine Adams (UC Davis) for guidance on DALY calculations, and
433 Adrienne Clermont and Victoria Chou (Johns Hopkins University) for assistance with population
434 numbers from LiST. The analysis was supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
435 (#1170661) and the UC Davis Medical Student Research Fellowship (AN and BW).

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Table 1: Prevalence of anemia and micronutrient deficiencies among women and children two years prior to and one year after introduction of fortified wheat flour in Cameroon¹

	Outcome	Prevalence of MNDs or anemia, Pre-Fortification		Prevalence of MNDs or anemia, Post-Fortification	
		%	SE	%	SE
WRA	Low Plasma Folate ²	30.1	4.3	0.3*	0.3
	Iron Deficiency ³	24.3	3.3	19.3	2.4
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency ⁴	8.0	2.5	1.8*	0.9
	Low Plasma Zinc ⁵	39.4	2.6	21.6*	3.3
	Anemia ⁶	46.7	2.7	39.1*	2.7
Children	Low Plasma Folate ²	12.5	2.4	0*	-
	Iron Deficiency ³	27.7	3.5	15.5*	2.1
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency ⁴	6.3	1.4	1.4*	0.7
	Low Plasma Zinc ⁵	46.8	3.9	28.4*	4.2
	Anemia ⁶	46.7	2.9	45.5	3.0

¹Values are percent \pm SE. Changes in iron deficiency in WRA and anemia in children were not statistically significant and thus were not included in the calculation of benefits. *Values were significantly different than those of the pre-fortification group, $P < 0.05$, as reported by Engle-Stone et al.¹¹

²Low plasma folate defined as < 10 nmol/L).

³Iron deficiency defined as inflammation-adjusted plasma ferritin concentration $< 12 \mu\text{g/L}$ for children or $< 15 \mu\text{g/L}$ for women.

⁴Vitamin B12 deficiency defined as $< 148 \text{pmol/L}$.

⁵Low plasma zinc defined as $< 50 \mu\text{g/dL}$ for pregnancy, $< 70 \mu\text{g/dL}$ for morning fasting samples, $< 66 \mu\text{g/dL}$ for morning nonfasting samples, and $< 59 \mu\text{g/dL}$ for afternoon samples among women, and $< 65 \mu\text{g/dL}$ for morning samples and $< 57 \mu\text{g/dL}$ for afternoon samples among children.

⁶Anemia defined as hemoglobin concentration $< 110 \text{g/L}$ for children and pregnant women or $< 120 \text{g/L}$ for nonpregnant women.

Table 2: Share of total fortification program costs applied to Yaoundé and Douala for startup and implementation of wheat flour fortification¹

Activity	13-Year Costs (2013 USD)	% of Total Cost
Baseline Survey	\$37,000	1.5%
Industrial Assessment	\$4,000	0.2%
Revision of Standards	\$11,000	0.5%
Equipment for Industry	\$2,000	0.1%
Micronutrient Premix	\$1,900,000	77.9%
Equipment for the National Lab	\$31,000	1.3%
Training of partners and stakeholders	\$8,000	0.3%
Launch Activities	\$12,000	0.5%
Supervision costs	\$131,000	5.4%
Other Indirect Costs	\$73,000	3.0%
Monitoring and evaluation	\$231,000	9.5%
Start-up Monitoring/Evaluation	\$124,000	5.1%
Ongoing Monitoring/Evaluation	\$107,000	4.4%
Total cost (undiscounted)	\$2,439,000	
3% Discount rate	\$1,989,000	
6% Discount rate	\$1,649,500	

¹Costs estimated from Kagin et al. ¹⁴ Premix and ongoing monitoring/evaluation are the only ongoing costs, all other costs are at start up. “Other indirect costs” include office rent and other materials.

Table 3. Proportion and number of women and preschool children reached by wheat flour

	Number reached in 2012	Number reached 10 years post-fortification, undiscounted	Number reached 10 years post-fortification, 3% discount	Number reached 10 years post-fortification, 6% discount
Women	1,227,200	14,157,200	11,984,700	10,264,800
Children	528,100	5,851,700	4,967,400	4,265,800
Total	1,755,300	20,008,900	16,952,100	14,530,600

fortification in Cameroon

¹Reach, defined as reported consumption of wheat flour-containing products in the prior 7 days, was 98% among women 15-49 y and children 12-59 mo in Yaoundé and Douala, Cameroon in 2009 (Engle-Stone et al 2012).

Table 4: Cases of anemia and micronutrient deficiencies averted in 2012 (year 1) and total case-years of anemia and micronutrient deficiencies averted 10 years post-fortification.

	Outcome	Cases averted in 2012	Case-years averted 10 years post-fortification, undiscounted	Case-years averted 10 years post-fortification, 3% discount	Case-years averted 10 years post-fortification, 6% discount
Women	Low Plasma Folate ¹	373,200	4,304,900	3,335,100	2,620,700
	Iron Deficiency ²	0	0	0	0
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency ³	77,600	895,700	693,900	545,300
	Low Plasma Zinc ⁴	222,900	2,571,400	1,992,100	1,565,400
	Anemia ⁵	95,200	1,097,900	850,600	668,400
Children	Low Plasma Folate ¹	67,400	746,400	579,800	456,800
	Iron Deficiency ²	83,500	746,300	635,700	547,800
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency ³	26,400	292,600	227,300	179,100
	Low Plasma Zinc ⁴	99,200	1,098,700	853,500	672,500
	Anemia ⁵	0	0	0	0
Total	Low Plasma Folate ¹	440,500	5,051,300	3,914,900	3,077,600
	Iron Deficiency ²	83,500	746,300	635,700	547,800
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency ³	104,000	1,188,200	921,200	724,300
	Low Plasma Zinc ⁴	322,100	3,670,100	2,845,600	2,237,900
	Anemia ⁵	95,200	1,097,900	850,600	668,400

¹Low plasma folate defined as <10 nmol/L).

²Iron deficiency defined as inflammation-adjusted plasma ferritin concentration <12µg/L for children or <15µg/L for women. Benefits are estimated be 0 for iron deficiency among women because no statistically significant difference was observed in iron deficiency prevalence among women pre- and post-fortification.

³B12 deficiency defined as <148pmol/L.

⁴Low plasma zinc defined as <50µg/dL for pregnancy, <70µg/dL for morning fasting samples, <66µg/dL for morning nonfasting samples, and <59µg/dL for afternoon samples among women, and <65µg/dL for morning samples and <57µg/dL for afternoon samples among children.

⁵Anemia defined as hemoglobin concentration <110g/L for children and pregnant women or <120g/L for nonpregnant women. Benefits are estimated be 0 for anemia among children because no statistically significant difference was observed in anemia prevalence among children pre- and post-fortification.

	Outcome	10 years, undiscounted (2013 USD)	10 years, 3% discount ¹ (2013 USD)	10 years, 6% discount (2013 USD)
Women				
	Reach	\$0.17	\$0.17	\$0.17
	Low Plasma Folate ²	\$0.57	\$0.60	\$0.63
	Iron Deficiency ^{3,4}	-	-	-
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency ⁵	\$2.72	\$2.87	\$3.02
	Low Plasma Zinc ⁶	\$0.95	\$1.00	\$1.05
	Anemia ⁷	\$2.22	\$2.34	\$2.47
Children				
	Reach	\$0.42	\$0.40	\$0.39
	Low Plasma Folate	\$3.27	\$3.43	\$3.61
	Iron Deficiency	\$3.27	\$3.13	\$3.01
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency	\$8.34	\$8.75	\$9.21
	Low Plasma Zinc	\$2.22	\$2.33	\$2.45
	Anemia ⁴	-	-	-
Total				
	Reach	\$0.12	\$0.12	\$0.11
	Low Plasma Folate	\$0.48	\$0.51	\$0.54
	Iron Deficiency	\$3.27	\$3.13	\$3.01
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency	\$2.05	\$2.16	\$2.28
	Low Plasma Zinc	\$0.66	\$0.70	\$0.74
	Anemia	\$2.22	\$2.34	\$2.47

Table 5: Cost per individual reached and cost per case-year of micronutrient deficiencies and anemia averted 10 years post-fortification, in USD (2013).

¹Both costs and benefits are discounted.

²Low plasma folate defined as <10 nmol/L).

³Iron deficiency defined as inflammation-adjusted plasma ferritin concentration <12µg/L for children or <15µg/L for women.

⁴Changes in iron deficiency among women and anemia among children were nonsignificant and not included in the analysis.

⁵B12 deficiency defined as <148pmol/L.

⁶Low plasma zinc defined as <50µg/dL for pregnancy, <70µg/dL for morning fasting samples, <66µg/dL for morning nonfasting samples, and <59µg/dL for afternoon samples among women,

and $<65\mu\text{g/dL}$ for morning samples and $<57\mu\text{g/dL}$ for afternoon samples among children.
⁷Anemia defined as hemoglobin concentration $<110\text{g/L}$ for children and pregnant women or $<120\text{g/L}$ for nonpregnant women.

	10 years, undiscounted	10 years, 3% discount	10 years, 6% discount
Cases averted	1,600	1,240	980
Cost/case averted	\$1,530	\$1,600	\$1,690

Table 6: Predicted cases and cost/case of neural tube defects averted 10 years post-fortification.

Table 7: Years of life lost, years lived with disability, total disability-adjusted life years, and cost per disability-adjusted life year averted for wheat flour fortification with iron and folic acid in Cameroon.

Timeline	Condition	Subtype	YLL Averted	Range	YLD Averted	Range	DALY Averted	Range	Cost/DALY Averted	Range
2012										
	NTD	Stillbirths	1,470		0		1,470			
		Livebirths	2,880	(2,680-3,040)	110	(230-10)	2,990	(2,910-3,050)		
		Total	4,350	(4,150-4,510)	110	(230-10)	4,460	(4,380-4,520)		
	Anemia ²	Mild	0		140		140			
		Moderate	0		1,400		1,400			
		Severe	0		310		310			
		Total	0		1,850		1,850			
	Total		4,350	(4,150-4,510)	1,960	(2,080-1,860)	6,310	(6,230-6,370)		
13-year, undiscoun- ted										
	NTD	Stillbirths	16,300		0		16,300			
		Livebirths	31,830	(29,670-33,660)	1,180	(2,530-80)	33,010	(32,200-33,740)		
		Total	48,130	(45,970-49,960)	1,180	(2,530-80)	49,310	(48,500-50,040)	\$49.50	(\$50.30-\$48.70)
	Anemia ²	Mild	0		1,560		1,560			
		Moderate	0		16,180		16,180			
		Severe	0		3,570		3,570			
		Total	0		21,310		21,310		\$114.50	
	Total		48,130	(45,970-49,960)	22,490	(23,840-21,390)	70,620	(69,810-71,350)	\$34.50	(\$34.90-\$34.20)

13-year, 3% discount										
	NTD	Stillbirths	12,660		0		12,660			
		Livebirths	24,720	(23,030- 26,130)	910	(1,970-60)	25,630	(25,000- 26,190)		
		Total	37,380	(35,690- 38,790)	910	(1,970-60)	38,290	(37,660- 38,850)	\$52.00	(\$52.80-\$51.20)
	Anemia ²	Mild	0		1,210		1,210			
		Moderate	0		12,540		12,540			
		Severe	0		2,760		2,760			
		Total	0		16,510		16,510		\$120.50	
	Total		37,380	(35,690- 38,790)	17,420	(18,480- 16,570)	54,800	(54,170- 55,360)	\$36.30	(\$36.70-\$35.90)
13-year, 6% discount										
	NTD	Stillbirths	9,970		0		9,970			
		Livebirths	19,470	(18,140- 20,580)	720	(1,550-50)	20,190	(19,690- 20,630)		
		Total	29,440	(28,110- 30,550)	720	(1,550-50)	30,160	(29,660- 30,600)	\$54.70	(\$55.60-\$53.90)
	Anemia ²	Mild	0		950		950			
		Moderate	0		9,850		9,850			
		Severe	0		2,170		2,170			
		Total	0		12,970		12,970		\$127.20	
	Total		29,440	(28,110- 30,550)	13,690	(14,520- 13,020)	43,130	(42,630- 43,570)	\$38.30	(\$38.70-\$37.90)

¹Values represent best estimate of YLL, YLD, and DALYs, and plausible ranges based on sensitivity analyses, as described in the text. DALY, disability-adjusted life year; NTD, neural tube defect; YLD, years lived with disability; YLL, years of life lost.

²YLL for anemia assumed to be 0 given that it is not a major contributor to mortality. Therefore, DALYs of anemia are made up of YLDs only. DALY = Disability-adjusted life year; YLL = Years of life lost; YLD = Years of life with disability; NTD = Neural tube defect

Table 8: Cases, DALYs and cost/DALY of NTDs averted assuming wheat flour fortification with folic acid at varying proportions of the target concentration¹

	Cases averted	NTD DALYs averted	Range	Cost/DALY averted	Range
25% target	1,190	36,700	(36,100-37,240)	\$66.50	(\$67.60-\$65.50)
50% target	1,600	49,310	(48,500-50,040)	\$49.50	(\$50.30-\$48.70)
75% target	1,710	52,750	(51,880-53,530)	\$46.20	(\$47.00-\$45.60)
100% target	1,780	55,050	(54,140-55,860)	\$44.30	(\$45.10-\$43.70)

¹Target fortification levels for folic acid in wheat flour in Cameroon are 5 mg/kg. DALY = disability-adjusted life year; NTD = neural tube defect